

S1 Text. Code-club topics explored by the 2022 organizing team.

1. PEP8; Basic Syntax and Variables.
2. Numeric operations (integers, floats, complex numbers); Comparison, Logical, and Boolean Operators
3. Indexing; methods and functions applied to Strings
4. Sequences (Tuples, Lists, Ranges)
5. Conditional statements (if, else, elif)
6. Sets
7. Loops (for, while)
8. Dictionaries
9. Functions and Recursive Functions
10. Input and Output formatting, and Import
11. NumPy
12. Data Manipulation with Pandas - Series
13. Data Manipulation with Pandas - DataFrame
14. Data Manipulation with Pandas - File Import and Exploration with Different Methods; exploratory statistical analyses
15. Data Cleaning and Preparation
16. Data Visualization with Matplotlib (parte 1)
17. Data Visualization with Matplotlib (parte 2)